

GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource:

Guide for assembling an assessment team

Actionable
version

Definition

An assessment team is a group of people with complementary expertise who design, manage, and implement research assessment (RA) processes. Teams can include professionals from research services, HR, library, IT, or external stakeholders.

This guide helps identify the types of expertise, roles and tasks required within a research assessment team. It is particularly useful for individuals responsible for designing, managing, or overseeing the assessment process.

Relevant SCOPE stages

This guide relates mainly to the early phases of the SCOPE Framework:

- Start with what you value: Identify values that should guide the composition of the team (e.g., diversity, fairness, openness).
- Context considerations: Ensure team expertise, roles, and composition fit the assessment's goals, scope, and institutional context.

When and how to use

- Planning assessments: When preparing a new research assessment process or reviewing existing processes.
- Recruitment and promotions: Assemble teams that combine disciplinary expertise with knowledge of open science and EDI principles.
- Strategic evaluations: Ensure inclusion of cross-disciplinary and stakeholder perspectives (e.g., industry, societal actors).
- Ongoing RRA reforms: Use diverse, rotating teams to bring in new perspectives and share lessons learned across the institution.

Guidance

Clarify roles and responsibilities

- Distinguish between planning, facilitation, and implementation roles.
- Clearly define leadership, coordination, and reporting responsibilities.

Ensure breadth of expertise

- Cover disciplinary knowledge, open science, EDI, ethical and cultural awareness, qualitative and quantitative methods, impact assessment, and data management.
- Balance permanent institutional staff with rotating experts.

Apply RRA principles.

- Follow guidance from e.g. DORA, CoARA, and Leiden Manifesto.
- Use chosen methods responsibly.
- Be mindful of unintended consequences, workload, and fairness.

Promote diversity and inclusion

- Ensure representation across career stages, genders, disciplines, and cultural backgrounds in the team.

Strengthen communication and efficiency

- Foster transparent dialogue among stakeholders.
- Share lessons learned across teams and institutions.
- Consider the cost-benefit balance of time-intensive evaluations.

Examples of roles and tasks

Roles / Expertise	Typical Tasks
Coordinator / Project Manager	Overall planning, coordination, reporting, communication
Disciplinary Expert	Provide field-specific knowledge
EDI Specialist	Ensure equity, diversity, and inclusion considerations
Open Science Expert	Promote open science practices
Data Analyst	Conduct quantitative analysis, data quality checks, visualization
Evaluator (peer review)	Qualitative assessment, impact evaluation, fairness checks

Further reading

GraspOS SCOPE+i Resources

- Stakeholder mapping template: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525686>
- Guide on principles for responsible research assessment for evaluators and evaluands: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526025>
- Checklist for Responsible Research Assessment: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15524455>
- Guide on Equity, Diversity and Inclusion (EDI) in Research Assessment: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526122>

- Institutional assessment process checklist:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526008>

Other

- Recommendations on research assessment processes (Science Europe, 2020). Position Statement <https://www.scienceeurope.org/media/3twjxm0/se-position-statement-research-assessment-processes.pdf>
- SCOPE Framework (INORMS, 2023): <https://doi.org/10.26188/21919527.v1>

